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SolACE - Solutions for improving Agroecosystem and Crop Efficiency for water and nutrient use

Deliverable 2.1

Genetic variation for yield performance and whole plant phenotype in bread and durum wheat germplasm

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1. Introduction

This deliverable reports on the results obtained in tasks 2.1 and 2.2, addressing the first two objectives of WP2, namely:

- analyse panels of wheat genotypes in phenotyping platforms to explore the variation of traits influencing resource availability, soil exploration and resource use under realistic water and N limitations.
- analyse wheat responses (yield and yield-related traits) to variations of resource availability in a network of field trials involving optimal conditions and combined water and N limitations.

The corresponding experiments in fields and phenotyping platforms have generated consequent datasets (ca. 500 genotypes of bread and durum wheat altogether, MS18 and MS34) that have been used for genetic analysis in WP4, for selection of contrasting genotypes in T2.4 and will be used for simulations in WP1 and T2.5. The current deliverable deals with the amplitude of variation for (and correlations between) yield, phenotype and environment data.

2. Work conducted

2.1 Assembly of bread and durum wheat panels

Two diversity panels, one bread wheat and one durum wheat, have been assembled, starting from existing core collections brought by the partners. The assembly had the main objective to bring a large genetic (and phenotypic) diversity, including a large proportion of cultivars, with a reasonably small window of earliness (to avoid confounding effects with drought-related responses) and with an appropriate genetic structure for genomic studies in WP4.

For bread wheat, within the framework of the BreedWheat project (ANR-10-BTBR-003), a panel of 450 winter wheat (named BWP3) has been assembled from 4600 accessions maintained in the INRAE Biological Resource Center in Clermont-Ferrand. The 450 accessions represented a global diversity adapted to European conditions in terms of earliness (between Récital and Apollo, early and late reference varieties) and plant height (60-120 cm) and maximizing the possibilities of detecting regions of interest (minimizing linkage disequilibrium). A subsample of 200 accessions was extracted for the SolACE project with a view to conserving maximum diversity on the basis of polymorphism at molecular markers. This subsample contains landraces, breeding lines, old and modern cultivars from 37 countries. This list has been extended with 10 hybrids and their 14 parents provided by Syngenta (see Annex 7.1).

The durum wheat panel has been assembled using similar criteria from different core collections. The panel comprised 192 lines from the core-set of ICARDA, CIMMYT, Italian, French and Spanish breeding germplasm brought by CREA, UNIBO and ARVALIS, and a set of 60 lines from an “Evolutionary Pre-breeding pOpulation” (acronym EPO) developed at INRAE-AGAP Montpellier since 1997 following a MAGIC-like crossing approach and enforced outcrossing with *T. turgidum* collection. In each set, a selection was conducted to optimise the population structure in anticipation of genomic studies in WP4.

2.2 Field experiments

Variety trials have been conducted in 2018 with the bread and durum wheat panels described above at different sites across Europe. The bread wheat trials have been conducted in Levroux (central France) by

SYNGENTA and in Gréoux (Southern France) by ARVALIS, while the durum wheat trials have been conducted at Foggia (Southern Italy) by CREA and at Mauguio (Southern France) by INRAE-AGAP Montpellier. Each trial involved, with two complete replicates, a control management treatment (standard N fertilisation / irrigated) and a low input treatment (standard N fertilisation minus 100 kg N/ha / rainfed). Point irrigation was applied in the rainfed treatment at some sites to avoid catastrophic yield losses where drought was becoming too severe. As discussed below, the N limitation has been achieved in most of the four trials. However, rain conditions in the spring and summer 2018 prevented the development of the expected water limitation at two sites.

Root samplings were performed in the Gréoux and Foggia sites to quantify the colonisation of roots by mycorrhizal fungi (AMF). The AMF data are presented in Deliverable 2.3, but will be referred to as well in this document.

2.3 Platform experiments

SolACE took advantage of the expertise in root phenotyping of two partners (INRAE-Agroécologie Dijon and UCLouvain) to analyse the root development of the two wheat panels under different angles. Three different phenotyping setups have been used in order to yield different sets of variables, as none of them was providing all variables that would allow us to evaluate how much each genotype realizes the different components of root system ideotypes (angles, branching, density, length,...). It was also important that our root data enable us to estimate the main parameters of root system architecture models used in T2.5, to allow the simulation of water and N use by all genotypes.

The specificities of these three setups are given in the following sections.

2.3.1 Pouches

This first setup consists of pouches on which young seedlings develop for a relatively limited time (2 to 3 days). It was implemented by UCLouvain. Seeds are “glued” on a 40 x 50 cm filter paper with a drop of agar, the filter paper adheres to a vertical PVC plate and the seedling is allowed to germinate in a humid atmosphere. Images are taken every day during three days and root systems are digitized using the SmartRoot software. The raw data from a pouch experiment is illustrated in Figure 1. From these polylines data, we computed the convex hull area, the angles between the left-most and right-most roots and the length of each root. The experiment has been replicated twice and, in each replicate, every genotype was present 5 times.

2.3.2 Rhizotubes

The 4PMI platform (INRAE-Agroécologie Dijon) is a high throughput phenotyping setup allowing the monitoring of plant growth for up to three weeks. 4PMI has developed innovative plant culture containers (RhizoTube) for automated dynamic and non-destructive in situ visualization of root systems at very high resolution (42 µm). In the SolACE experiment, water and N availability were reduced by limiting the supply of water and the concentration of N in the substrate. Pictures of the shoot and root are taken once a day, and plant parts are weighted at the end of the experiment. From these images and measurements, the depth and width of the root system, the convex hull and projected area, as well as mass and root:shoot ratio were computed (Figure 2). The whole panels have been grown in two replicates (650 rhizotubes per panel).

Figure 1. Illustration of pouches experiment data. Each graph is an overlay of the 10 seedling root systems of the corresponding genotype vectorized with SmartRoot. From this data, convex hull area, angles and length can be derived.

Figure 2. Illustration of rhizotube data. From left to right: raw image, bounding rectangle (from which width and depth are estimated), convex hull and segmented root (from which projected root system area is computed).

2.3.3 Aeroponics

The RootPhAir platform (UCLouvain) is a high throughput phenotyping setup in which roots unfold in 3D, without any mechanical impedance and with a uniform supply of water and nutrients in the form of a mist. This aeroponic facility allows the growth and monitoring of root system during up to three weeks. This platform has been designed to achieve a high temporal resolution (2 hours) that allows the estimation of dynamic variables (elongation rate, branching frequency) in addition to angles, length and diameters. The data processing is largely built on the localisation of root tips and their movement over time (

Figure 3). As images are taken from a unique view point, so that projection- and occlusion-derived effects cannot be easily handled. The whole panels have been grown in four replicates.

Figure 3. Illustration of RootPhAir data. Left: raw image (last image of that plant). Right: overlay of tips coordinates during the whole growth period.

3. Bread wheat results

3.1 Field experiments

3.1.1 Summary

The variety trial on the bread wheat panel has been conducted at two locations in France: Levroux (Syngenta) and Gréoux (Arvalis). Despite common management rules for water and N, the specific rainfall at each location influenced the outcome of the trial.

Figure 4 summarises the conditions of the Gréoux trial. The low water and N management reduced the grain yield through a reduction of ear number and grain number, without effect on grain weight. The grain protein content was strongly reduced, which indicates that N was actually limiting. However, the management had only a slight effect on the area of the penultimate leaf. This, combined with the exceptionally rainy season for this site, suggest that the crop was not markedly limited by water but only by an early N stress.

Figure 4. Boxplot of bread wheat genotypes performance under control (HN-WW) vs low water and N (LN-WD) in the Gréoux trial. From left to right: grain yield (GWAM, q/ha), spike number (EDAD, spikes/m²), grain number (GNUMBER, grains/m²), thousand kernels weight (TKWH, g), grain protein concentration (GPR_PCT_D, %) and penultimate leaf area (LAREA, cm²).

The effect of management on grain yield was much more pronounced at the Levroux station, presumably due to a reduction of the grain number (Figure 5). This suggests that water was limiting early in the season. Grain protein content was also very much decreased by low N and water, as was canopy development (plant height). The Levroux trial therefore yielded the expected scenario of low water and N, with a reasonably strong effect on crop variables.

Figure 5. Summary of bread wheat genotypes performance under control (HN-WW) vs low water and N (LN-WD) in the Levroux trial. From left to right: grain yield (GWAM, q/ha), spike number (EDAD, spikes/m²), thousand kernels weight (TKWH, g), grain protein concentration (GPR_PCT_D, %) and plant height (PH, cm).

The amplitude of variation between genotypes is summarized in Table 1. It was somehow larger in control conditions and in the Gréoux trial. At both locations, grain yield was among the variables with the widest amplitude, along with grain number and plant height. On the opposite, phenology, grain weight, grain size and grain protein content displayed much smaller amplitudes.

Table 1. Amplitude of variation in the bread wheat panel. Reported values are coefficients of variation (%) of the distribution of adjusted genotypic means for the indicated variables.

	Gréoux		Levroux	
	HN_WW	LN_WD	HN_WW	LN_WD
Grain yield	17.98	9.38	9.51	12.30
Spike number	11.77	5.21	8.87	8.48
Grain number	17.24	11.46		
Thousand kernels weight	11.86	8.23	4.21	1.65
Grain surface	7.77	3.44		
Grain protein concentration	7.90	7.25	7.01	5.44
Penultimate leaf area	16.28	12.79		
Plant height			17.30	13.86
Flag ligule appearance	2.98	3.50		
Spike emergence	4.71	2.83	4.48	4.45

3.1.2 Grain yield and yield components

The distribution and responses of bread wheat for yield-related variables are shown in Figure 6 and Figure 7.

Figure 6. Scatter plot of yield-related responses for bread wheat in the Gréoux trial. HN-WW: high nitrogen and irrigated; LN-WD: (control - 100 kg N/ha) and rainfed. Dotted line: 1:1 reference. Red line: linear regression.

Figure 7. Scatter plot of yield-related responses for bread wheat in the Levroux trial. HN-WW: high nitrogen and irrigated; LN-WD: (control - 100 kg N/ha) and rainfed. Dotted line: 1:1 reference. Red line: linear regression.

In the Gréoux trial, an important diversity of responses to crop management was observed for yield and spike number, indicated by important residuals around the regression line (not shown). The diversity was less important for grain number, suggesting that part of the constraints on spike number were compensated by the spike development (grain number / spike). Residuals for grain weight and protein content were much smaller, indicating a better conservation of genotypes ranking, despite strong effects of low N on grain protein content.

The diversity of responses to management in the Levroux trial was relatively lower than in the Gréoux trial, as was observed for the diversity of genotypic means (Table 1). Nevertheless, residuals were relatively important for these variables.

3.1.3 Phenology

Figure 8 and Figure 9 display the distributions and responses of bread wheat genotypes for phenology.

Figure 8. Scatter plot of phenology-related responses for bread wheat in the Gréoux trial. HN-WW: high nitrogen and irrigated; LN-WD: (control - 100 kg N/ha) and rainfed. Dotted line: 1:1 reference. Red line: linear regression.

Figure 9. Scatter plot of phenology-related responses for bread wheat in the Levroux trial. HN-WW: high nitrogen and irrigated; LN-WD: (control - 100 kg N/ha) and rainfed. Dotted line: 1:1 reference. Red line: linear regression.

As indicated by rather small residuals, the ranking of genotypes phenology was not much affected by the management, except for spike emergence which tended to occur a bit earlier for late varieties, particularly in Gréoux.

3.1.4 Canopy development

Figure 10 displays the distributions and responses of bread wheat genotypes for canopy development. Clearly, genotypes with large penultimate leaves in Gréoux, and tall genotypes in Levroux were more affected by the low water and N management than the other ones, which suggests that these genotypes had a larger demand for soil resources and were therefore more limited than the others by the low availability of these resources.

Figure 10. Scatter plot of canopy development-related responses for bread wheat in the Gréoux (left) and Levroux (right) trials. HN-WW: high nitrogen and irrigated; LN-WD: (control - 100 kg N/ha) and rainfed. Dotted line: 1:1 reference. Red line: linear regression.

3.1.5 Conclusions from field experiments

The aim of these experiments was to assess the level of genotypic variability for agronomic variables and their responses to low water and N in the bread wheat panel. The two trials converge towards an important amplitude of variation for most variables, which is exploited in WP4 for genetic analysis, in WP2 for the selection of contrasting lines and in WP1 for the modelling of durum wheat responses in European scenarios. This dataset will be further analysed in T2.4 and T2.5, where the specificities of the four scenarios (2 managements x 2 sites) will be accounted for via environmental data captured in the experiments.

3.2 Platform experiments

3.2.1 Summary

Root system architecture variables were measured on the bread wheat panel on three platforms: 4PMI (INRAE-Agroécologie Dijon), pouches and RootPhAir (UCLouvain). A quantitative summary of the genetic diversity of variables observed in platforms is given in Table 2, using the coefficient of variation and the broad sense heritability.

The coefficient of variation has been chosen as a measure of the amplitude of variation between genotypes. For example, a value of 20% indicates that 68% of the genotypes embrace a relative amplitude of 40% (+/- 20% around the panel average), which is already an important diversity if we consider that 32% of the genotypes are beyond this range.

Broad-sense heritabilities indicate how much the genotypic variance accounts for the phenotypic variance. Heritabilities tended to be different between platforms. They ranged between 0.11 and 0.57 in RootPhAir but were all above 0.51 for 4PMI and above 0.70 for pouches. The lower values of RootPhAir likely result from the image acquisition method, as all measurements in RootPhAir are made on 2D projections of 3D root systems and are therefore subject to projection effects which depend on the (random) orientation of the plant relative to the camera.

Table 2. Heritabilities and amplitude of variation (CV) of root variables in bread wheat (CV has been computed from the adjusted genotypic means). Variables are listed in four categories: embryonic root-related, lateral-root related, root system shapes-related and biomass-related). LRP: lateral root primordia.

	Platform	H ²	CV %
Number of embryonic roots	RootPhAir	0.42	14.83
Embryonic root length	Pouches	0.75	19.89

Embryonic root elongation rate	RootPhAir	0.48	11.19
Maximum root length	RootPhAir	0.31	13.77
Maximum root length	4PMI	0.73	11.67
Embryonic root diameter	RootPhAir	0.30	12.50
Embryonic root angle	Pouches	0.70	15.28
Seminal root angle	RootPhAir	0.46	35.94
Lateral root diameter	RootPhAir	0.57	7.27
LRP duration of development	RootPhAir	0.11	14.19
Lateral root density	RootPhAir	0.41	39.28
Convex Hull Area	4PMI	0.61	32.79
Convex Hull Area	Pouches	0.83	42.55
Cumulated root length	Pouches	0.81	23.26
Root system projected area	4PMI	0.74	24.76
Root system width	4PMI	0.55	30.40
Root dry mass	RootPhAir	0.23	30.50
Root dry mass	4PMI	0.66	22.84
Shoot dry mass	RootPhAir	0.29	28.49
Shoot dry mass	4PMI	0.69	23.93
Root:shoot ratio	RootPhAir	0.51	11.34
Root:shoot ratio	4PMI		11.89

3.2.2 Assessment of diversity by variable categories

The diversity of each variable is examined in the subsequent sections. Variables are listed in four categories: related to embryonic roots, related to lateral roots, related to the root system shape and related to the plant biomass. Variables from the first two categories describe the behaviour of individual roots with respect to the main processes driving root system morphogenesis: growth, tropism and branching. Variables from the third and fourth categories can be seen as “integrative” variables because their variability integrates the variability of growth, tropism and branching, for the different root types and during the growth period. These integrative variables are usually easier to capture than those related to individual roots. They are also often considered as close to the functions of the root system (e.g. soil volume explored, root length density,...).

3.2.2.1 Embryonic roots (seminal and primary)

The combination of the three platforms provides a fairly detailed assessment of embryonic root diversity of the bread wheat panel, embracing embryonic root numbers, elongation, tropism and diameter.

The number of embryonic roots (Figure 23) ranges from 3 to 7. This corresponds to plants producing one to three pairs of seminal roots in addition to the primary root, which is the whole range of values described in the literature for wheat. The coefficient of variation (15%) is reasonable, yet the heritability is medium (0.42). We cannot advocate a RootPhAir effect for this medium value since the number of embryonic roots is established early after germination (before the plant is actually influenced by the aeroponics conditions) and it was estimated manually, with no (or little) measurement errors.

The elongation rate of embryonic roots can be assessed by the average embryonic root length in the pouch experiment (3-day old seedling). It was also estimated directly in the RootPhAir platform from the elongation of all embryonic roots during a 15-day long period (Figure 24). The coefficient of variation is higher for young

seedlings in pouches (20%) compared to 15-day old plants in aeroponics (11%). The heritability is also higher in pouches (0.75) compared to aeroponics (0.48). It is likely that the genotypic variability of seed mass (observed, but not measured) led to early root growth differences, which disappeared as the seedling switched to the autotrophic state.

An integrated value of embryonic root elongation rate is also given by the maximum root length, that was observed in 4PMI and RootPhAir (Figure 25). Unlike the previous variable, this value corresponds to a single embryonic root, usually the oldest (named primary here). The amplitude of variation is similar to the previous variables (11.7% in 4PMI, 13.8% in RootPhAir). The heritability is high in 4PMI (0.73) but is much smaller in RootPhAir (0.31).

The diameter of embryonic roots, considered as a predictor of potential elongation rate, has been measured in RootPhAir (Figure 26). Its amplitude of variation (12.5%) is similar to that of the elongation rate, but its heritability is lower (0.30). The estimation error of root diameter, being a small discrete number of pixels, is larger than that of root length, and that increase cannot be accounted for by any genotype effect.

The angle between left- and right-bound embryonic roots is often considered as a precursor of the lateral spread of the root system. It was measured in pouches (from the left- and right-most embryonic) and in RootPhAir (from the first pair of embryonic roots, therefore with a smaller amplitude) (Figure 27). RootPhAir revealed a larger variation (35.9%) between the first pair of embryonic roots than did pouches on the last pair (15.3%). The heritability for these variables was high for pouches (0.70) and medium for RootPhAir (0.46). The lower value for RootPhAir results probably from a larger error variance due to the projection effect of the 3D root structure on 2D images, which is expected to be most expressed on traits such as angles.

On the whole, these results indicate that wheat breeding has left a rather large amplitude of variation for most variables related to embryonic roots, which are expected to be very important for early resource capture and plant establishment in the field. In particular, the two variables that affect the root system lateral spread, namely the number of embryonic roots (the larger the number of roots, the wider the spread), and the angle amplitude between the first pair of embryonic roots both display an important variability.

The large values of the heritabilities suggest that these variables can still be under the effect of selection, or at least that a strong selection pressure has not been active. Yet, the striking differences between the heritabilities in RootPhAir and those in the other platforms remain to be tackled.

3.2.3 Lateral roots

The RootPhAir platform has been designed to estimate variables related to lateral roots. It is probably the first time that such detailed lateral root traits are delivered on a large diversity panel. Lateral roots are important drivers of root system function as they represent most of the root-soil contact surface.

The lateral root density (number of lateral roots branching from one centimeter of embryonic root) is likely to be a determinant factor of the root length density in soils (Figure 28). We found a very large variability between genotypes (39%), with a medium heritability (0.41). The important incidence of roots overlapping in projected images has two consequences: one is to bias the estimated means towards smaller values, and the other is to increase the error noise. The average value (around 2 LR.cm⁻¹) certainly underestimates the real number of lateral roots, and the heritability is thereby lowered.

Another important variable related to lateral root is the duration of development of lateral root primordia (LRP). This variable is rarely estimated, but has been shown to be an important driver of root shape by root system architecture models. It can also be seen as an indicator of competition for assimilates between the apical growth of the embryonic root and the nearby developing LRP. We have found an important variability

for this variable (14.2%) (Figure 29). However, its heritability is negligible (0.11), which indicates that its environmental variability must be very large.

The third variable is the lateral root diameter which, as mentioned for embryonic roots above, is thought to be an indicator of potential lateral root elongation (Figure 30). The observed amplitude of variation is small (7%), but this is not surprising as the anatomical structure of lateral roots constraints the possibilities for size variation. Interestingly, this is the RootPhAir variable for which the heritability was the highest (0.57).

On the whole, the bread wheat panel used in SolACE displays an important variability for lateral root-related variables. In addition, lateral root density and lateral root diameter (a proxy of potential elongation rate) display a relatively high heritability, if we take into account the measurement error due to the RootPhAir platform.

3.2.4 Integrative variables

Variables relative to the shape of the root system have been observed on 3-day old (pouch) and 15-day old (rhizotube) seedlings. They were not estimated from the RootPhAir dataset since root system shape in aeroponics is modified by effects of gravity which leads long roots to bend downwards.

The first integrative variable that was computed is the area of the convex hull (smallest convex polygon in which the whole root system can fit), which is a surrogate for the volume of soil explored (Figure 31). The convex hull area displays a very large amplitude of variation (4PMI: 33%; pouches: 42%) and it has a high heritability (4PMI: 0.61; pouches: 0.83). From a theoretical point of view, this variable is positively influenced by elongation rate (which increases the root system depth) and embryonic root angle (which increases the horizontal spread of the root system). The actual correlations between these variables are discussed in the section 3.2.6.

The second integrative variable is the cumulated root length, which embraced embryonic and lateral roots (Figure 32). In the 4PMI platform, the cumulated root length was approached by the projected root area, assuming relative root diameter variability is smaller than the relative length variability. The cumulated root length displays a large amplitude of variation (4PMI: 25%; pouches: 23%) and it has a high heritability (4PMI: 0.74; pouches: 0.81). From a theoretical point of view, this variable is positively influenced by the number of embryonic roots, the root elongation rate or diameter (which determines the individual root length) and the lateral root density (which determines the number of lateral roots). The actual correlations between these variables are discussed in the section 3.2.6.

The last integrated variable that we computed is the root system width, taken as the width of the smallest rectangle in which the whole root system can fit (Figure 33). This variable was estimated in the 4PMI platform. It shows a large amplitude (30%) and a medium heritability (0.55). From a theoretical point of view, this variable is positively influenced by the number of embryonic roots, the root elongation rate or diameter (which determines the individual root length) and the embryonic root angle. The actual correlations between these variables are discussed in the section 3.2.6.

3.2.5 Biomass variables

The root and shoot biomasses have been measured in the 4PMI and RootPhAir platform on 15-day old plants. The amplitude of variation was slightly lower in the 4PMI (respectively 24 and 23%) compared to RootPhAir (respectively 31 and 28%), while the heritabilities were higher in 4PMI (respectively 0.66 and 0.69) than in

RootPhAir (respectively 0.23 and 0.29). These differences between platforms converge towards a hypothesis that the inter-plant variability in the RootPhAir platform was larger than in 4PMI.

From these variables, we computed the root:shoot ratio (Figure 34), which indicates how much the plant invests in root vs shoot growth. This variable had a small amplitude of variation (11% in 4PMI and RootPhAir). The heritability in RootPhAir was the second highest in the platform (0.51) and was approximately twice those of shoot and of root mass. The larger heritability and the similarity of the CV between platforms suggests that relative allocation to root and shoot was better conserved across platforms than were the absolute root and shoot masses.

Figure 34 indicates that the root:shoot ratio in 4PMI was larger than in RootPhAir. Among the many differences of growing conditions, the low water and N availability in RootPhAir may have contributed to a relatively stronger allocation to the root system.

3.2.6 Correlations between platform variables

We initiated the analysis of the correlations between all variables (within and across platforms) with a principal component analysis (PCA). This analysis revealed mostly differences in plant size and between platforms. The first principal component (PC1) accounted for 20.0% of the total variation and was capturing scale variation for all variables. PC1 was therefore only helpful to discriminate between tall and small genotypes. PC2 accounted for 15.9% of the variation and was clustering 4PMI variables against all others. Similarly, PC3 accounted for 13.1% and clustered most pouches variables against all others. The correlations of interest were therefore hidden in the following components, yet these accounted individually for less than 10% of the variation. The outcome of the PCA was therefore rather limited.

Figure 11 presents the correlations between all traits listed in Table 2 and discussed above. The graph has been simplified by removing any correlation that is not significant at $\alpha=0.01$.

It appears that almost all significant correlations occur between variables measured in the same platform, against only six between variables from different platforms. This observation results partly from the small number of common variables across platforms, but also partly from an absence of significant correlations between common (or at least similar) variables. The latter indicates a small level of repeatability across platforms and calls for caution when extrapolating the observations from one platform to other conditions (e.g. many scientists still consider that phenotyping platforms data are predictive of field performance).

Figure 11. Correlation matrix between all root traits from platforms for bread wheat. Correlations that are not significant at $\alpha=0.01$ are not shown. Variable naming conventions: «er» : embryonic roots; «lr» : lateral roots; «lrp» : lateral root primordium; «rs» : root system; «ch» : convex hull; «sh» : shoot; «RPA» : RootPhAir. Other abbreviations are straightforward.

Within the set of pouch-derived variables, embryonic angle is slightly correlated with embryonic length. Not surprisingly, the two variables are strongly correlated with the convex hull area.

Within the set of 4PMI-derived variables, all but the root:shoot ratio are positively correlated with one another. Not surprisingly, each of these integrated variables is linked with plant size or area. The shoot:root ratio is positively correlated with root mass and negatively correlated with shoot mass, which suggests that, in bread wheat breeding, changes of root:shoot are contributed by both (and opposite) shoot and root variation. Surprisingly, the root:shoot ratio correlates negatively (slightly) with the convex hull area, the projected area and the root system width, three variables that correlate positively with root and shoot mass. This would suggest that variations of root:shoot ratio also involve variations of specific root length (or root diameter) and angles, two variables that were not observed in 4PMI.

Within the set of RootPhAir-derived variables, few significant correlations were found and they are, for most, rather small. The main exceptions are root and shoot mass that correlate strongly with the embryonic root number, the embryonic root elongation rate, the maximum embryonic root length and the lateral root diameter, all indicative of root size. An interesting positive correlation was found between lateral root and embryonic root diameters, suggesting that these variables are not necessarily antagonistic. The same two variables correlate with the embryonic root angle, which could be meaningful as plants with wider angles leave more space between embryonic roots where lateral root can grow further without competing with each other. Finally, there was a small but negative correlation between the number of embryonic roots and the lateral root density, suggesting that resources supporting the formation of lateral roots might be shared among embryonic roots.

The six correlations between variables of different platforms are the following: a positive correlation between embryonic root angle in pouches and embryonic root number in RootPhAir, supplementary embryonic roots growing more horizontally than the first pair; consistently positive correlations between embryonic root angle in pouches, on the one side, and embryonic root angle in RootPhAir, convex hull area in 4PMI and root system width in 4PMI on the other side; a positive correlation between root:shoot ratio in 4PMI and in RootPhAir; and a slight positive correlation between root system mass in 4PMI and in RootPhAir

3.2.7 Conclusions from platform experiments

The aim of these experiment was to assess the level of genotypic variability for root variables in the bread wheat panel. The three platform converge towards an important amplitude of variation for most variables, with heritabilities generally high in at least two platforms. The panel seems therefore suitable for the genetic analysis conducted in WP4 and for the selection of contrasting lines to be used in T2.4.

The small correlations between variables within platform (except for integrative and correlated variables) suggest that these variables are not genetically correlated and/or that they have not been under consistent selection forces. This result needs to be confirmed, but would indicate that, at least if narrow sense heritabilities were sufficient (remember that these experiments only allow to estimate broad-sense heritability), these variables could be selected independently to generate different root system ideotypes.

The differences between platforms are questioning, even if the number of common variables was limited. Except for root:shoot ratio, all other common variables were not or only slightly correlated between platforms. If we consider that the pouch, rhizotubes and aeroponics root environments are closer to one another than they are to any soil, this questions the very significance of root phenotypes observed in a single platform. The fact that root:shoot ratio is the only variable to be relatively conserved between 4PMI and RootPhAir is interesting: allocation to root would be more conserved than how assimilates are used to grow the root system.

The RootPhAir platform provided many component variables, but most of them had small heritabilities. The large amplitude and small heritabilities for root and shoot mass in RootPhAir, which are less subject to measurement errors, indicate an important inter-plant variability in the experiments. Different hypotheses could be explored. For example, it has sometimes been observed that stress conditions amplify the expression of genotypic differences between genotypes. In the same line, it has been recently proposed that root morphogenesis would depend on stochastic processes whose outcome can be influenced by impeding factors, if these are sufficiently strong. Finally, the possibility remains that growing conditions in the aeroponics experiments were not optimal for a subset of plants or genotypes.

3.3 Field-platform correlations

An in-depth analysis of field and platform data is planned in the context of T2.4 on a selection of 40 genotypes and in the context of T2.5 (functional structural plant-crop modelling). Here, we took a naive approach of analysing crude correlations between agronomic and root variables (Figure 12). On the agronomic side, variables were chosen to represent yield, protein concentration, phenology and canopy. As the root side is more exploratory, all variables have been taken into account.

Figure 12. Correlation matrix between platform root traits and selected agronomic traits from field bread wheat. Correlations that are not significant at $\alpha=0.01$ are not shown. Variable naming conventions: «er» : embryonic roots; «lr» : lateral roots; «lrp» : lateral root primordium; «rs» : root system; «ch» : convex hull; «sh» : shoot; «RPA» : RootPhAir. «GY»: grain yield; «GPC»: grain protein content; «HEAD»: heading date; «LA»: leaf area. Other abbreviations are straightforward.

As suspected from so different environment and variables, the correlations are usually low. Our interpretation should therefore focus on patterns of correlations involving more than two variables or that are consistently observed across the sites and/or platforms.

Some correlations were expected, as the negative correlations between root:shoot ratio (in 4PMI and RootPhAir) and plant height. Among interesting correlations, we find positive ones between early root elongation (pouch experiment) and canopy development in both field trials.

Rather intriguing are negative correlations between root mass (or root:shoot ratio) (in 4PMI and RootPhAir) and heading date. A plausible explanation is that the formation of nodal roots in wheat follows that of new shoot nodes. If we can assume that shoot node formation runs more slowly in late genotypes, then the number of nodal roots (and the root mass) at 15 days (time of root harvest in the two platforms) should be smaller as well.

It is tempting to develop hypotheses on each of these correlations, but one has to remember that these numbers remain small. Their analysis will be continued in T2.4 and T2.5, where the data reported here will be combined with additional trials.

4. Durum wheat results

4.1 Field experiments

The variety trial on the durum wheat panel has been conducted at two locations, Mauguio (France, INRAE-AGAP Montpellier) and Foggia (Italy, CREA). As for bread wheat, and despite common management rules for water and N, the specific pluviometry at each location influenced the outcome of the trial.

Figure 13 summarises the conditions of the Foggia trial. The low water and N management did not affect grain yield. Presumably, early water deficit slightly affected the number of grains, yet this was compensated by exceptionally favourable conditions during the rest of the season. The grain protein content was slightly reduced, indicating mitigated N limitation. However, the management had only a slight effect on plant height. On the whole, the crop was probably not limited by water, and not strongly by N.

Figure 13. Summary of durum wheat genotypes performance under control (HN-WW) vs low water and N (LN-WD) in the Foggia trial. From left to right: grain yield (GWAM, q/ha), thousand kernels weight (TKWH, g), grain protein concentration (GPR_PCT_D, %) and plant height (PH, cm).

The effect of management on grain yield was more pronounced at the Mauguio location in France. Yield components indicate a strong reduction of grain number and a strong compensation in terms of grain weight (Figure 14). This suggests that water was limiting early in the season. Grain protein content was also very much decreased by low N and water. Management effect on canopy development (plant height) was, however, limited, most probably because of unusually rainfall in the springtime. The Mauguio trial therefore yielded the expected scenario of low water and N, with a reasonably strong effect on crop variables.

Figure 14. Summary of durum wheat genotypes performance under control (HN-WW) vs low water and N (LN-WD) in the Mauguio trial. From left to right: grain yield (GWAM, q/ha), grain number (GNUMBER, grains/m²), thousand kernels weight (TKWH, g), grain protein concentration (GPR_PCT_D, %) and plant height (PH, cm).

The amplitude of variation between genotypes is summarized in Table 3. As for bread wheat, it was somehow larger in control conditions and in the trial where management effect was reduced (Foggia). At both locations, grain yield and grain number displayed the widest amplitude. On the opposite, phenology (except flag ligule appearance), grain weight, grain size and grain protein content displayed much smaller amplitudes.

Table 3. Amplitude of variation in the durum wheat panel. Reported values are coefficients of variation (%) of the distribution of adjusted genotypic means for the indicated variables.

	Foggia		Mauguio	
	HN_WW	LN_WD	HN_WW	LN_WD
Grain yield	23.26	17.86	15.42	13.45
Grain number			15.64	14.78
Thousand kernels weight	9.76	9.13	8.49	7.66
Grain specific surface			5.74	3.81
Grain protein concentration	6.32	5.83	6.63	5.59
Plant height	10.20	10.58	7.88	7.03
Flag ligule appearance	17.62	11.88		
Spike emergence	11.71	10.99	3.29	2.55
Physiological maturity	2.87	2.83	1.74	1.61

4.1.1 Yield and yield components

Figure 15 and Figure 16 display the yield and yield component responses of durum wheat genotypes to low water and N management.

In the Foggia trial, where actual limitations turned out to be minor, an important diversity of responses (residuals to the regression line) was observed for yield and grain weight. The diversity was much smaller for grain protein concentration, as was observed in the wheat trial of Gréoux where target scenarios were not fully reached.

Figure 15. Scatter plot of yield-related responses for durum wheat in the Foggia trial in Italy. HN-WW: high N and irrigated; LN-WD: (control - 100 kg N/ha) and rainfed. Dotted line: 1:1 reference. Red line: linear regression.

The situation seemed different in the Mauguio trial where an important diversity of responses was observed for all yield-related variables, including grain protein concentration.

Figure 16. Scatter plot of yield-related responses for durum wheat in the Mauguio trial in France. HN-WW: high N and irrigated; LN-WD: (control - 100 kg N/ha) and rainfed. Dotted line: 1:1 reference. Red line: linear regression.

4.1.2 Phenology

The phenological responses of durum wheat genotypes to low water and N management are plotted in Figure 17 and Figure 18. The diversity of responses was rather large in the Foggia trial: the amplitude of residuals was about 5 days, which is one third of the amplitude of genotypic means in the panel.

Figure 17. Scatter plot of phenology-related responses for durum wheat in the Foggia trial in Italy. HN-WW: high N and irrigated; LN-WD: (control - 100 kg N/ha) and rainfed. Dotted line: 1:1 reference. Red line: linear regression.

In the Mauguio trial, heading and maturity tended to occur earlier for late varieties than for early ones. The diversity of responses was small at spike emergence and slightly increased at maturity, indicating the

genotype-specific responses in the combined stress were not fully acquired early in the cycle and developed along the season.

Figure 18. Scatter plot of phenology-related responses for durum wheat in the Mauguio trial in France. HN-WW: high N and irrigated; LN-WD: (control - 100 kg N/ha) and rainfed. Dotted line: 1:1 reference. Red line: linear regression.

4.1.3 Canopy development

Figure 19 shows the canopy development responses of durum wheat genotypes. As for bread wheat, tall genotypes were more affected by the low water and N management than the other ones, which suggests that these genotypes had a larger demand for soil resources and were therefore more limited than the other ones by the low availability of these resources.

Figure 19. Scatter plot canopy development (plant height) responses for durum wheat in the Foggia (left) and Mauguio (right) trials. HN-WW: high N and irrigated; LN-WD: control - 100 kg N/ha) and rainfed. Dotted line: 1:1 reference. Red line: linear regression.

4.1.4 Relations with AMF colonisation

The Foggia trial also involved observations of mycorrhizae (AMF) for all genotypes in control conditions. These data are presented in Deliverable 2.3, but we take the opportunity to analyse them here in relationship with agronomic variables (Figure 20). There was globally no significant correlations between AMF colonisation and yield, grain protein content and earliness (regression slopes were not significant). One can only observe that they are systematically positive, in the sense that some late and high yielding varieties with higher grain protein content may be better colonised than early ones. In the same line, we could not find any relation between AMF colonisation and yield response to crop management.

Figure 20. Relationship between root AMF colonisation and agronomic variables in the Foggia trial in Italy.

4.1.5 Conclusions from field experiments

The aim of these experiments was to assess the level of genotypic variability for agronomic variables and their responses to low water and N in the durum wheat panel. The two trials converge towards an important amplitude of variation for most variables, which is exploited in WP4 for genetic analysis, in WP2 for the selection of contrasting lines and in WP1 for the modelling of durum wheat responses in European scenarios.

4.2 Platform experiments

4.2.1 Summary

A quantitative summary of the genetic diversity of variables observed in platforms is given in Table 4, using the coefficient of variation and the broad sense heritability (see section 3.2.1 for a justification of these indicators).

4.2.2 Assessment of diversity by variable categories

The diversity of each variable is examined in the subsequent sections. As for bread wheat, variables are listed in four categories: related to embryonic roots, related to lateral roots, related to the root system shape and related to the plant biomass. For durum wheat, we also consider the different subpanels in our interpretation of the distribution of genotypic means.

4.2.2.1 Embryonic roots (seminal and primary)

The combination of the three platforms provides a fairly detailed assessment of embryonic root diversity of the durum wheat panel, embracing embryonic root numbers, elongation, tropism and diameter.

The number of embryonic roots (Figure 35) ranges from 3 to 7. This corresponds to plants producing one to three pairs of seminal roots in addition to the primary root, which is the whole range of values described in the literature for wheat. The coefficient of variation (13%) is reasonable, yet the heritability is medium (0.41). These range and heritabilities are similar to those of bread wheat, however, a much larger proportion of durum wheat genotypes have ca. 5 embryonic roots, irrespective of the sub-panel.

Table 4. Heritabilities and amplitude of variation (CV) of root variables in durum wheat. (CV has been computed from the adjusted genotypic means). Variables are listed in four categories: embryonic root-related, lateral-root related, root system shapes-related and biomass-related). LRP: lateral root primordia.

	Platform	H^2	CV (%)
Number of embryonic roots	RootPhAir	0.41	13.08
Embryonic root length	Pouches	0.77	19.14
Embryonic root elongation rate	RootPhAir	0.30	11.38
Maximum root length	RootPhAir	0.21	16.62
Maximum root length	4PMI	0.81	13.25
Embryonic root diameter	RootPhAir	0.27	12.23
Embryonic root angle	Pouches	0.65	11.19
Seminal root angle	RootPhAir	0.33	40.08
Lateral root diameter	RootPhAir	0.38	7.20
LRP duration of development	RootPhAir	0.00	14.69
Lateral root density	RootPhAir	0.28	44.5
Convex Hull Area	4PMI	0.67	40.07
Convex Hull Area	Pouches	0.87	41.97
Cumulated root length	Pouches	0.85	24.01
Root system projected area	4PMI	0.68	28.43
Root system width	4PMI	0.66	36.73
Root dry mass	RootPhAir	0.27	36.41
Root dry mass	4PMI	0.66	25.17
Shoot dry mass	RootPhAir	0.28	34.29
Shoot dry mass	4PMI	0.68	23.12
Root:shoot ratio	RootPhAir	0.42	11.92
Root:shoot ratio	4PMI		11.52

The elongation rate of embryonic roots can be assessed by the average embryonic roots in the pouch experiment (3-day old seedling). It was also estimated directly in the RootPhAir platform from the elongation of all embryonic roots during a 15-day long period (Figure 36). The durum wheat panel average was roughly 10% higher than that of bread wheat. The coefficient of variation is higher for young seedling in pouches (19%) compared to 15-day old plants in aeroponics (11%). The heritability is also higher in pouches (0.77) compared to aeroponics (0.30). It is likely that the genotypic variability of seed mass (observed, but not measured) led to early root growth differences, which disappeared as the seedling switched to the autotrophic state. These results are very similar to those of bread wheat, except a much smaller heritability in RootPhAir. The EPO and UNIBO sub-panels displayed smaller values in pouches only, which could be due to a slight delay in germination. In RootPhAir, the GPDUR sub-panel was slightly shifted towards larger values of elongation rate.

The maximum root length was observed in 4PMI and RootPhAir (Figure 37). It corresponds to a single embryonic root, usually the oldest (named primary here). The amplitude of variation is similar to the previous variables (13% in 4PMI, 17% in RootPhAir). The heritability is high in 4PMI (0.81) but is much smaller in RootPhAir (0.21). These results are very similar to those of bread wheat. In both platforms, the UNIBO sub-panel was slightly shifted towards smaller values. In RootPhAir only, GPDUR was slightly shifted towards larger values, consistent with what was seen for the elongation rate.

The diameter of embryonic roots, considered as a predictor of potential elongation rate, has been measured in RootPhAir (Figure 38). Its amplitude of variation (12.5%) is similar to that of the elongation rate, but its heritability is lower (0.27). These figures are very close to those of bread wheat. Consistent with its slightly larger elongation rate and maximum root length, the GPDUR sub-panel was slightly shifted towards larger root diameters.

The angle between left- and right-bound embryonic roots was measured in pouches (from the left- and right-most embryonic) and in RootPhAir (from the first pair of embryonic roots, therefore with a smaller amplitude) (Figure 39). RootPhAir revealed a larger variation (40%) between the first pair of embryonic roots than did pouches on the last pair (11%). The heritability for these variables was high for pouches (0.65) and medium for RootPhAir (0.33). These results are similar to those of bread wheat, except for a smaller heritability in RootPhAir for durum wheat. The slight differences between the sub-panels in pouches was not observed in RootPhAir.

On the whole, these results were fairly similar to those of bread wheat, if only smaller heritabilities in RootPhAir, and lead to similar conclusions in terms of diversity. The differences between sub-panels were small and not particularly consistent across platforms.

4.2.3 Lateral roots

The lateral root density has been estimated in the RootPhAir platform (Figure 40). We found a very large variability between genotypes (45%), with a small heritability (0.28). As for bread wheat, the average value (around 2.5 LR.cm⁻¹) certainly underestimates the real number of lateral roots, and the same is probably true for the heritability. The amplitude of variation seemed narrower in the GPDUR sub-panel than in the three other panels.

As for bread wheat, the duration of development of lateral root primordia showed an important variability (14.2%) with a negligible heritability (0.00, not estimable) (Figure 41). The variability between genotypes is therefore likely to be the consequence of the smaller number of replicates.

The lateral root diameter was measured, as an indicator of potential lateral root elongation (Figure 42). As for bread wheat, the observed amplitude of variation is small (7%) but the heritability was higher (0.38).

On the whole, the durum wheat panel used in SolACE displays an important variability for lateral root-related variables. As for embryonic root related variables, heritabilities for durum wheat were generally smaller than those estimated for bread wheat, and a sub-panel effect was not apparent.

4.2.4 Integrative variables

Variables relative to the shape of the root system have been observed on 3-day old (pouch) and 15-day old (rhizotube) seedlings.

The area of the convex hull (smallest convex polygon in which the whole root system can fit) (Figure 43) displays a very large amplitude of variation (4PMI: 40%; pouches: 42%) and it has a high heritability (4PMI: 0.67; pouches: 0.87). The smaller values of the EPO and UNIBO sub-panels in pouches is consistent with their smaller average root length mentioned above. The actual correlations between the convex hull area and its component variables are discussed in the section 4.2.6.

The cumulated root length distribution (or its approximation based on projected root area) are shown on Figure 44. The cumulated root length displays a large amplitude of variation (4PMI: 28%; pouches: 24%) and it has a high heritability (4PMI: 0.68; pouches: 0.85). Again, the smaller values of the EPO and UNIBO sub-

panels in pouches is consistent with their smaller average root length mentioned above. The actual correlations between cumulated root length and its component variables are discussed in the section 4.2.6.

The root system width distribution, estimated in the 4PMI platform, is shown on Figure 45. It shows a large amplitude (37%) and a medium heritability (0.66). The GPDUR sub-panel was slightly shifted towards smaller values. The actual correlations between root system width and its component variables are discussed in the section 4.2.6.

Generally, the results obtained for these integrative variables were fairly similar to those obtained for bread wheat. The heritabilities in 4PMI tended to be higher for durum wheat than for bread wheat.

4.2.5 Biomass variables

The root and shoot biomasses have been measured in the 4PMI and RootPhAir platform on 15-day old plants. The amplitude of variation was slightly lower in the 4PMI (respectively 25 and 23%) compared to RootPhAir (respectively 36 and 34%), while the heritabilities were higher in 4PMI (respectively 0.66 and 0.68) than in RootPhAir (respectively 0.27 and 0.28). These figures are very close to those of breadwheat.

From these variables, we computed the root:shoot ratio (Figure 46). This variable had a small amplitude of variation (12% in 4PMI and RootPhAir). The heritability in RootPhAir was the second highest in the platform (0.42) and was nearly twice those of shoot and of root mass. As for bread wheat, the larger heritability and the similarity of the CV between platforms suggests that relative allocation to root and shoot was better conserved across platforms than were the absolute root and shoot masses. In both platforms, the GPDUR sub-panel was slightly shifted towards larger values. The root:shoot ratio in 4PMI was larger than in RootPhAir, yet the difference was smaller than in the bread wheat case, which may indicate that durum wheat was less affected than bread wheat by the low water and N availability in the 4PMI platform.

4.2.6 Correlations between platform variables

As for bread wheat, a principal component analysis on all platform variables mostly revealed differences in plant size and between platforms. PC1 accounted for 18.8% of the variability and captured scale variation of all variables; PC2 accounted for 15.1% of the variability and was clustering most RootPhAir variables against all other variables; PC3 accounted for 11.7% of the variability and clustered most pouches variables against all other variables.

Figure 21 presents the correlations between all traits listed in Table 4 and discussed above (only correlations that are significant at $\alpha=0.01$ are shown).

As for bread wheat, most significant correlations occur between variables measured in the same platform. The number of significant correlations between variables from different platforms (19) is however higher than for bread wheat (6), even if their values are usually small.

Within the set of pouch-derived variables, embryonic angle is slightly correlated with embryonic length. Not surprisingly, the two variables are strongly correlated with the convex hull area.

Figure 21. Correlation matrix between all platform root traits for durum wheat. Correlations that are not significant at $\alpha=0.01$ are not shown. Variable naming conventions: «er» : embryonic roots; «lr» : lateral roots; «lrp» : lateral root primordium; «rs» : root system; «ch» : convex hull; «sh» : shoot; «RPA» : RootPhAir. Other abbreviations are straightforward.

Within the set of 4PMI-derived variables, all but the root:shoot ratio are positively correlated with one another. The shoot:root ratio is only positively correlated with root mass. Unlike bread wheat, it is not correlated with shoot mass, which suggests that, along durum wheat breeding, changes of root:shoot are contributed mostly by root mass variation. The root:shoot ratio displays a slightly positive correlation with root system depth and a slightly negative one with root system width. There is therefore a slight tendency for durum wheat genotypes with a high root allocation to grow deeper and less shallow than those with a smaller root allocation.

Within the set of RootPhAir-derived variables, few significant correlations were found and they are, for most, rather small. The main exceptions are root and shoot mass that correlate strongly with the embryonic root number, the embryonic root elongation rate, the maximum embryonic root length and the lateral root diameter. As for bread wheat, a positive correlation was found between lateral root and embryonic root diameters, suggesting that these variables are not necessarily antagonistic. The embryonic root angle did not correlate with any other variable. Finally, as for bread wheat, there was a small but negative correlation between the number of embryonic roots and the lateral root density, suggesting that resources supporting the formation of lateral roots might be shared among embryonic roots.

Among platforms, the results for durum wheat seemed more consistent than they were for bread wheat, even if the correlations tended to be small. The length and convex hull area in pouches correlate with the corresponding variables in 4PMI. Also the maximum root length in 4PMI correlates with that in RootPhAir. The lateral root diameter in RootPhAir (an indicator of potential lateral root elongation) was also positively correlated with the convex hull area and the root system width in 4PMI. Finally, as for bread wheat, the root:shoot ratio in 4PMI and RootPhAir were positively correlated.

4.2.7 Conclusions from platform experiments

The aim of these experiment was to assess the level of genotypic variability for root variables in the durum wheat panel. The three platform converge towards an important amplitude of variation for most variables, with heritabilities generally high in at least two platforms. The panel seems therefore suitable for the genetic analysis conducted in WP4 and for the selection of contrasting lines to be used in T2.4.

As for bread wheat, the small correlations between variables within platform (except for integrative and correlated variables) suggest that these variables are not genetically correlated and/or that they have not been under consistent selection forces.

The differences between platforms are also questioning, yet are more encouraging than for bread wheat. More common variables were at least slightly correlated between platforms.

Finally, the heritabilities in the RootPhAir platform were in many instances smaller than their corresponding values for bread wheat. Again, understanding this observation will require more investigations.

4.3 Correlations between field and platform variables

As for bread wheat, we took a naive approach of analysing crude correlations between agronomic and root variables (Figure 22). On the agronomic side, variables were chosen to represent yield, protein concentration, phenology and canopy. As the root side is more exploratory, all variables have been taken into account.

Figure 22. Correlation matrix between platform root traits and selected agronomic traits from field durum wheat. Correlations that are not significant at $\alpha=0.01$ are not shown. Variable naming conventions: «er» : embryonic roots; «lr» : lateral roots; «lrp» : lateral root primordium; «rs» : root system; «ch» : convex hull; «sh» : shoot; «RPA» : RootPhAir. «GY»: grain yield; «GPC»: grain protein content; «HEAD»: heading date; «LA»: leaf area. Other abbreviations are straightforward.

We found fewer correlations here than for bread wheat, and they tended to be larger. Again, our interpretation will focus on patterns of correlations involving more than two variables or that are consistently observed across the sites and/or platforms.

A consistent correlation was found between lateral root diameter (an indicator of potential lateral root expansion) and grain protein content (at the two sites). Given the role attributed to lateral roots in N uptake, this correlation is rather interesting. That relation might contribute to the large correlation between root mass in 4PMI and grain protein content at the two field sites.

As for bread wheat, the root:shoot ratio in RootPhAir is well correlated with grain yield in the trial that was N-limited only, and not correlated with grain yield in the trial that was both water- and N-limited. This is an intriguing result that deserves more careful analysis. Also intriguing are the positive correlations between that same root:shoot ratio and heading date at the two sites. These correlations were negative for bread wheat (between 4PMI and the two sites).

It is tempting to develop hypotheses on each of these correlations, but one has to remember that these numbers remain small. Their analysis will be continued in T2.4, where the data reported here will be combined with additional trials.

5. Conclusions

The aims of T2.1 and T2.2 were to explore the bread and durum wheat diversity (i) for root growth and morphology and (ii) for agronomic performance and responses to combined water and N limitation. To reach this objective, we have combined high throughput phenotyping platforms (that are part of the EPPN2020 network) and conventional field trials.

Several bread and durum wheat core collections have been used to create a bread wheat and a durum wheat diversity panel of ca. 200 genotypes each, that have been augmented with modern hybrids (bread wheat panel) and lines from a pre-breeding population (durum wheat panel). These panels have been designed to embrace a large genotypic and phenotypic diversity while minimising genetic structure.

Field trials were conducted at four locations to assess the level of genotypic variability for agronomic variables and their responses to low water and N in the two panels. All trials converge towards an important amplitude of variation for most agronomic variables. Colonisation by AMF fungi was also evaluated in one of the durum wheat trials (Foggia, Italy), yet did not reveal significant correlations with agronomic variables.

In order to assess the genotypic variability for root growth and morphology, the two panels have been analysed in state-of-the-art high throughput phenotyping platforms, namely 4PMI at INRAE-Agroécologie Dijon and RootPhAir at UCLouvain (that are both part of the EPPN2020 network). The list of root variables embraced root-level features (elongation rate, diameter, tropism) as well as whole root system or whole plant features.

Results from the two platforms converge towards an important amplitude of variation for most root variables, with moderate to large heritabilities. The panels seem therefore suitable for the genetic analysis conducted in WP4 and for the selection of contrasting lines to be used in T2.4.

The small correlations between variables within platform (except for integrative and correlated variables) suggest that these variables are not genetically correlated and/or that they have not been under consistent selection forces. Assessing the dimensionality of root system is one of the objectives of an ongoing joint-platform experiment in the EPPN2020 project (to which 4PMI and RootPhAir are contributing). The SolACE results suggest that the dimensionality might be larger than expected. This result needs to be confirmed, but would indicate that, at least if narrow sense heritabilities were sufficient (remember that these experiments only allow to estimate broad-sense heritability), these variables could be selected independently to generate different root system ideotypes.

Despite contrasting environments and variables, interesting (yet weak) correlations were observed between some platform variables and agronomic performance. It is tempting to develop hypotheses on these correlations, but one has to remember that these correlations are small. Their analysis will be continued in T2.4, where the data reported here will be combined with additional trials.

6. Partners involved in the work

Table 5: Partners contribution to T2.1 and T2.2

Task	ARVALIS	CREA	INRAE-Agroécologie	INRAE-AGAP	INRAE-GDEC	INRAE-LEPSE	SYNGENTA	UCLouvain
Provided core collections and prepared panels	✓	✓		✓			✓	
Conducted SolACE field trial and provided data	✓	✓		✓				
Conducted SolACE platform data and provided data			✓					✓
Assembled data templates						✓		✓
Performed statistical analysis	✓				✓	✓		✓
Participated in deliverable writing	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓

7. Annexes

7.1 List of genotypes in the bread and durum wheat panels

BREAD WHEAT PANEL			DURUM WHEAT PANEL		
SolACE.Code Name		Partner/Collection	SolACE.Code Name		Partner/Collection
SBW1001	BENNI	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1001	AGATHE	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1002	BONNY	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1002	ALEXIS	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1007	JACOMETTI 49	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1003	ANVERGUR	PANEL_GPDUR
SBW1008	KLEIN 32	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1004	ARCOUR	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1010	MCNAIR 1587	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1005	ARGELES	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1011	MONON	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1006	ATHORIS	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1012	MV03-86	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1007	ATOUDUR	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1014	OBRII	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1008	AVENTUR	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1016	ROMA	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1009	BABYLONE	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1019	ZG7865/83	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1010	BYBLOS	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1021	BOURGOGNE	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1011	CHISTERA	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1023	TALDOR	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1012	CLOVIS	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1024	MIRONOVSKAIA 31	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1013	COUSSUR	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1026	FRUNZENSKAIA 60	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1014	CULTUR	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1027	GONCHA	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1015	DAKTER	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1028	308.02.2/WEAVER//F362K2.121	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1016	DAURUR	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1029	DEMAR-4	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1017	DURIAAC	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1030	ZG3073/84	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1018	DUROBONUS	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1031	OWL/Col No.3625//SOISSONS	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1019	FLORIDOU	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1034	BOLAL	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1020	GIBUS	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1038	HATVANI 40/25	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1021	ISILDUR	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1039	KARCAGI 149	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1022	KARUR	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1040	MCNAIR 701	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1023	LAHAN	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1041	MONTJOIE	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1024	LGBORIS	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1045	SCOUT66	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1025	LIBERDUR	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1047	TAM108	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1026	LUMINUR	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1048	TRAYANA	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1027	MEMPHIS	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1049	LORETO	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1028	MIRADOUX	PANEL_GPDUR
SBW1051	MACNAIR1813	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1029	MONASTIR	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1055	ZITNICA	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1030	MONDUR	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1056	BERMET	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1031	MURANO	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1058	SWM89Y074H	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1032	NEMESIS	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1060	AKULA/BONITO//F10S-3	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1033	NOBILIS	PANEL_GPDUR
SBW1061	BONITO//KAREE/TUGELA	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1034	PASTADOU	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1062	KL.ESTRELLA	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1035	PESCADOU	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1064	MUSTANG	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1036	PHARAON	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1066	2109-36	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1037	PICTUR	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1067	2678-6	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1038	PLUSSUR	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1068	2838-39	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1039	QUALIDOU	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1069	ALBIDUM	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1040	RELIEF	PANEL_GPDUR
SBW1070	ARPADHALOM-16	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1041	RGTFABIONUR	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1071	AUTONOMIA	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1042	RGTVOILUR	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1072	BUCKSKIN	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1043	SCULPTUR	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1073	CARSON	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1044	SYBANCO	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1080	STACY	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1045	SYCISCO	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1081	WHEELER	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1046	TABLUR	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1082	ZGIPK.4387	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW1047	TOMCLAIR	FSOVGPDUR
SBW1083	VIENNOY	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2001	ADONE	crea
SBW1085	GEREK79	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2002	AKENATON	crea
SBW1091	TAMEX	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2003	ALEMANNO	crea
SBW1094	COUGAR	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2004	AMBRAL	crea
SBW1096	SKOPJANKA	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2005	ANCO_MARZIO=Yupare	crea
SBW1101	CAPET	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2006	ANTALIS	crea
SBW1102	COLORBEN-4	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2007	ARNACORIS	crea
SBW1105	DACIA	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2008	ARTEMIDE	crea
SBW1108	FOISON	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2009	AUREO	crea
SBW1110	GK-KALAKA	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2010	BALIDURO	crea
SBW1111	HOKUEI	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2011	BRONTE	crea

SBW1112	MUTSUBENKEY	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2012	CAPPELLI	crea
SBW1114	NECTAR	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2013	CASANOVA	crea
SBW1115	NS RANA 1	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2014	CICLOPE	crea
SBW1119	ROSE	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2015	CORE	crea
SBW1120	RUBIS	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2016	CUSPIDE	crea
SBW1121	SADOVOSUPER	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2017	DARIO	crea
SBW1124	TECUMSEH	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2018	Desert_King_(oro)	crea
SBW1126	SALMONE	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2019	DORATO	crea
SBW1127	KOTARE	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2020	DYLAN	crea
SBW1129	MADRIGAL	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2021	ERCOLE	crea
SBW1135	TILEK	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2022	FABULIS	crea
SBW1137	MCGUIRE	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2023	FURIO_CAMILLO	crea
SBW1144	TCI960735	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2024	GENNARO	crea
SBW1146	AGROUNIA	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2025	GHIBLI	crea
SBW1147	BRACO	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2026	GIUSTO	crea
SBW1148	CEREALOR	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2027	GLOCODUR	crea
SBW1149	CHAMBORD	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2028	ISMUR	crea
SBW1150	DECLIC	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2029	Kanakis	crea
SBW1151	HOROSHIRI KOMUGI	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2030	KARALIS	crea
SBW1154	SOLARIS	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2031	KRONOS	crea
SBW1158	MIRONOVSKAIA 30	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2032	L22D84=PR22D84	crea
SBW1163	MV309-99	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2033	L2574	crea
SBW1165	GR915	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2034	MARAKAS	crea
SBW1169	ES14/SITTA//AGRI/NAC	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2035	MG_54	crea
SBW1170	BILINMIYEN96.40	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2036	MIDYNU	crea
SBW1171	TCI962395	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2037	MINOSSE	crea
SBW1172	QUENOA INIA	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2038	NEGRIDURO	crea
SBW1173	ADENA	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2039	OFANTO	crea
SBW1178	ALBATROS	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2040	OVIDIO	crea
SBW1179	LUNA	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2041	PAPADAKIS	crea
SBW1181	LUTESCENS CH65/85	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2042	PICENO	crea
SBW1186	REDLAND	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2043	PR22D89	crea
SBW1188	SALUDA	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2044	QUADRATO	crea
SBW1194	BRANKA	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2045	RAMIREZ	crea
SBW1196	NOBLET	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2046	SACHEM	crea
SBW1199	WWL860104	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2047	SAN_CARLO	crea
SBW1201	BRUTA	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2048	SERAFQ_NICK	crea
SBW1204	CIT89073	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2049	SIJAH_KILAKLI	crea
SBW1206	GK ZUGOLY	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2050	SILUR	crea
SBW1207	ODESKA 161	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2051	STRONGFIELD	crea
SBW1211	MV314-99	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2052	SURAKA	crea
SBW1213	P29	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2053	SURMESUR	crea
SBW1216	PROWERS 99	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2054	SVEVO	crea
SBW1217	TAISETSU KOMUGI	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2055	TIREX	crea
SBW1218	MAGISTRAL	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2056	TIZIANA	crea
SBW1219	GARAGUM	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2057	TORRESE	crea
SBW1220	PAT	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2058	VETRODUR	crea
SBW1221	CRVENA ZVESDA	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2059	ARIOSTO	crea
SBW1224	HOSAR	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2060	DORAL	crea
SBW1225	SUSQUEHANNA	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2061	ASTERIX	crea
SBW1228	DI7003-1-12	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2062	BALSAMO	crea
SBW1231	LUTESCENS EG16/82	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2063	CAPDUR	crea
SBW1234	MV23-77	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2064	ELIOS	crea
SBW1235	NEUHOF 1	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2065	FENICE	crea
SBW1241	TORRIL	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2066	MATT	crea
SBW1245	ARTHUR	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2067	OLIVER	crea
SBW1249	MV-MAGVAS	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2068	Selcuklu-97	crea
SBW1250	ALKA	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW2069	SY_EXPERT	crea
SBW1255	MIRLEBEN	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3001	JOYAU	unibo-2017
SBW1258	RAMPART	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3002	SARAGOLLA	unibo-2015
SBW1266	ECRIN	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3003	NADIF	unibo-2017
SBW1268	HERKULES	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3004	CICCIO	unibo-2015
SBW1276	LANGUEDOC	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3005	TEXTUR	unibo-2017
SBW1279	MV33-86	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3006	TEODORICO	unibo-2017
SBW1280	PROBSTDORFER MARTIN	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3007	ACADUR	unibo-2017
SBW1282	TIMMO	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3008	ACHILLE	unibo-2017
SBW1283	UTE	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3009	ALDEANO-DP028	unibo-2015
SBW1284	SIROKA	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3010	AMMAR-1-DP122	unibo-2015

SBW1287	830-22	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3011	AW12/BIT-DP060	unibo-2015
SBW1288	MV30-86	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3012	BOLIDO-DP034	unibo-2015
SBW1292	PROBSTDORFER ACCORD	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3013	CASTELDOUX	unibo-2017
SBW1297	SANRAFAEL	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3014	CESARE	unibo-2017
SBW1300	ORMIL	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3015	CYMMIT67-PLATA16-DP016	unibo-2015
SBW1301	BEHERT	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3016	COLOMBO	unibo-2017
SBW1302	MIRONIVSKA 68	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3017	CREDIT	unibo-2017
SBW1304	CDC-CLAIR	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3018	GEROMTEL-1-DP139	unibo-2015
SBW1308	MALYSA	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3019	GIBALTAR	unibo-2017
SBW1310	SANSA	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3020	GIDARA-2-DP141	unibo-2017
SBW1311	CAMINO	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3021	CHABA88-DP065	unibo-2017
SBW1314	ALTERNA-TOURNEUR	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3022	INRAM1808=AMRIA-DP049	unibo-2015
SBW1315	ARGEE	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3023	JAWHAR-DP053	unibo-2015
SBW1316	CH73641	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3024	JORDAN-DP150	unibo-2015
SBW1317	DI7202-103	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3025	KIKO-NICK	unibo-2017
SBW1319	DRUZHBA	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3026	LAGONIL-2	unibo-2015
SBW1320	GERMINAL	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3027	LLOYD	unibo-2015
SBW1324	NUGAINES	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3028	LOUKOS-1_DP157	unibo-2015
SBW1325	OVEST	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3029	MARJANA-DP054	unibo-2015
SBW1326	P4523-80	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3030	NEFER-DP205	unibo-2015
SBW1327	PAGEANT	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3031	OBELIX	unibo-2017
SBW1328	PEGASUS	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3032	OMGENIL-3_DP166	unibo-2015
SBW1332	RIDA	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3033	OMRABI-5_DP071	unibo-2015
SBW1334	ULM	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3034	ORT-1_DP170	unibo-2015
SBW1338	CH73425	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3035	PLINIO_DP107	unibo-2015
SBW1341	HOLZAPFELS FRUH WEIZEN	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3036	ROQUENO_DP110	unibo-2015
SBW1345	SIMONA	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3037	TITO_FLAVIO	unibo-2017
SBW1346	SEMPER	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3038	ATIL_C2000_DP252	unibo-2015
SBW1348	ABEL	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3039	CHAM-1_DP136	unibo-2015
SBW1353	CHARMANY	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3040	CRESO_DP089	unibo-2015
SBW1354	COURTAL	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3041	GALLARETA_DP041	unibo-2015
SBW1355	ERSHOVSKAJA-3	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3042	KOFA	unibo-2015
SBW1356	FANION	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3043	ARDENTE	unibo-2015
SBW1358	FLORIO	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3044	AZEGHAR-2_DP128	unibo-2015
SBW1359	MALACCA	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3045	BOLO_DP035	unibo-2015
SBW1360	PRESTIGE	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3046	PATKA_3_DP011	unibo-2015
SBW1361	PRIMEPI	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3047	CLAUDIO	unibo-2015
SBW1362	PROBSTDORFER GEBER	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3048	COLORADO_DP086	unibo-2015
SBW1364	RINNER WINTERWEISEN	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3049	CORTEZ_DP088	unibo-2015
SBW1365	STADLER	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3050	DURCAL_DP039	unibo-2015
SBW1366	STETSON	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3051	GRAZIA_DP096	unibo-2015
SBW1370	YORKSTAR	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3052	GUEROU-1_DP142	unibo-2015
SBW1372	MAXIMUM CAMBIER	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3053	IRIDE	unibo-2015
SBW1373	FERDINAND	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3054	KARIM_DP064	unibo-2015
SBW1374	ROD	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3055	LEVANTE	unibo-2017
SBW1377	EDWIN	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3056	MERIDIANO_DP005	unibo-2015
SBW1378	BOVICIUS	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3057	MIKI-1_DP161	unibo-2015
SBW1380	DI37-12-2	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3058	MOHAWK_DP104	unibo-2015
SBW1390	FROIDURE	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3059	SIMETO_DP248	unibo-2015
SBW1392	SIRIA	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3060	ZEINA-1_DP075	unibo-2015
SBW1393	REGINA	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3061	ACALOU_DP190	unibo-2015
SBW1398	IWWRN(85)198	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3062	ARCOBALENO_DP080	unibo-2015
SBW1403	MIRONOVSKAIA 264	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3063	COLOSSEO_DP087	unibo-2015
SBW1406	REIVAL	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3064	ITALO_DP098	unibo-2015
SBW1407	ROISEL	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3065	KABIR-1_DP151	unibo-2015
SBW1408	TAMBO	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3066	MASSARA-1_DP160	unibo-2015
SBW1410	VERBESSERTER ST.JOHANNER	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3067	MEXICALI-75_DP103	unibo-2015
SBW1411	BIZEL	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3068	NEODUR	unibo-2017
SBW1412	CAROLUS	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3069	NORMANNO	unibo-2017
SBW1413	CH73241	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3070	ODISSEO	unibo-2017
SBW1415	DANKOWSKA IDEALNA	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3071	OUASERL-1_DP172	unibo-2015
SBW1417	DI7210-15-11	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3072	QUADALETE_DP176	unibo-2015
SBW1425	ZETA	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3073	VALNOVA_DP114	unibo-2015
SBW1426	ALTER DE GEMBLOUX	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3074	WB881_DP116	unibo-2015
SBW1427	COMPACT	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3075	AUS1_DP125	unibo-2015
SBW1428	FERMO	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW3076	MARZAK_DP055	unibo-2015
SBW1429	GELPA	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW4001	EL4X_27	EPO
SBW1435	PROTEKTOR	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW4002	EL4X_29	EPO

SBW1436	TRUBILO	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW4003	EL4X_31	EPO
SBW1437	VAKKA	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW4004	EL4X_35	EPO
SBW1439	REICHERSBERG 42	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW4005	EL4X_41	EPO
SBW1441	AUBE	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW4006	EL4X_117	EPO
SBW1444	BONTARIS	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW4007	EL4X_118	EPO
SBW1446	ATUT-II	BreedWheat Diversity Panel	SDW4008	EL4X_120	EPO
SBW2001	ALLEZ Y	Checks from ARVALIS	SDW4009	EL4X_130	EPO
SBW2002	APACHE	Checks from ARVALIS	SDW4010	EL4X_145	EPO
SBW2003	BERMUDE	Checks from ARVALIS	SDW4011	EL4X_146	EPO
SBW2004	RUBISKO	Checks from ARVALIS	SDW4012	EL4X_176	EPO
SBW2005	TRAPEZ	Checks from ARVALIS	SDW4013	EL4X_179	EPO
SBW2006	HOCHLAND	Checks from ArchiRac	SDW4014	EL4X_182	EPO
SBW3001	ANTEQUERA	Local variety from partners	SDW4015	EL4X_188	EPO
SBW3002	CH NARA	Local variety from partners	SDW4016	EL4X_192	EPO
SBW3003	LUDWIG	Local variety from partners	SDW4017	EL4X_194	EPO
SBW3004	NOGAL	Local variety from Spain	SDW4018	EL4X_195	EPO
SBW3005	WIWA	Local variety from partners	SDW4019	EL4X_198	EPO
SBW4001	AKAMAR	SYNGENTA parents	SDW4020	EL4X_207	EPO
SBW4002	ARLEQUIN:B-	SYNGENTA parents	SDW4021	EL4X_212	EPO
SBW4003	ATHLON:B-	SYNGENTA parents	SDW4022	EL4X_222	EPO
SBW4004	BOLOGNA:B-	SYNGENTA parents	SDW4023	EL4X_227	EPO
SBW4005	CCB09H046:B-	SYNGENTA parents	SDW4024	EL4X_229	EPO
SBW4006	GIAMBOLOGNA:B-	SYNGENTA parents	SDW4025	EL4X_233	EPO
SBW4007	H15FR11757:B-	SYNGENTA parents	SDW4026	EL4X_240	EPO
SBW4008	H15FR13047:B-	SYNGENTA parents	SDW4027	EL4X_241	EPO
SBW4009	OREGRAIN:B-	SYNGENTA parents	SDW4028	EL4X_243	EPO
SBW4010	SUBLIM:B-	SYNGENTA parents	SDW4029	EL4X_250	EPO
SBW4011	SY 116464:B-	SYNGENTA parents	SDW4030	EL4X_252	EPO
SBW4012	SY 117071:B-	SYNGENTA parents	SDW4031	EL4X_262	EPO
SBW4013	SY 117079:B-	SYNGENTA parents	SDW4032	EL4X_268	EPO
SBW4014	SY MATTIS:B-	SYNGENTA parents	SDW4033	EL4X_278	EPO
SBW5001	ANNIBALE/AKAMAR	SYNGENTA hybrids	SDW4034	EL4X_292	EPO
SBW5002	BOLOGNA/GIAMBOLOGNA	SYNGENTA hybrids	SDW4035	EL4X_305	EPO
SBW5003	H15FR11757/SY MATTIS	SYNGENTA hybrids	SDW4036	EL4X_316	EPO
SBW5004	H15FR13047/OREGRAIN	SYNGENTA hybrids	SDW4037	EL4X_331	EPO
SBW5005	SUBLIM/ATHLON	SYNGENTA hybrids	SDW4038	EL4X_344	EPO
SBW5006	SUBLIM/GIAMBOLOGNA	SYNGENTA hybrids	SDW4039	EL4X_350	EPO
SBW5007	SUBLIM/OREGRAIN	SYNGENTA hybrids	SDW4040	EL4X_368	EPO
SBW5008	SY 116464/ATHLON	SYNGENTA hybrids	SDW4041	EL4X_370	EPO
SBW5009	SY 117071/ARLEQUIN	SYNGENTA hybrids	SDW4042	EL4X_372	EPO
SBW5010	SY 117079/AKAMAR	SYNGENTA hybrids	SDW4043	EL4X_373	EPO
			SDW4044	EL4X_401	EPO
			SDW4045	EL4X_402	EPO
			SDW4046	EL4X_407	EPO
			SDW4047	EL4X_412	EPO
			SDW4048	EL4X_426	EPO
			SDW4049	EL4X_428	EPO
			SDW4050	EL4X_435	EPO
			SDW4051	EL4X_460	EPO
			SDW4052	EL4X_464	EPO
			SDW4053	EL4X_474	EPO
			SDW4054	EL4X_476	EPO
			SDW4055	EL4X_483	EPO
			SDW4056	EL4X_488	EPO
			SDW4057	GQ4X_75	EPO
			SDW4058	GQ4X_139	EPO
			SDW4059	EL4X_453	EPO
			SDW4060	EL4X_504	EPO

7.2 Genotypic means distributions from bread wheat platforms experiments

7.2.1 Embryonic roots (seminal and primary)

7.2.1.1 Number of embryonic roots

Figure 23. Distribution of the number of embryonic roots in bread wheat (adjusted genotypic means).

7.2.1.2 Primary root elongation rate

Figure 24. Distribution of embryonic root length in bread wheat (adjusted genotypic means). Left panel: average root length in the pouch experiment (3-days old seedlings). Right panel: elongation rate of the oldest embryonic root (primary) in the aeroponics experiment (estimated over a 15 day-long period).

Figure 25. Distribution of the length of the longest embryonic root (usually the oldest) in bread wheat (adjusted genotypic means). Left panel: rhizotube experiment (15-day old plants). Right panel: aeroponics experiment (15 day-old plants).

7.2.1.3 Embryonic root diameter

Figure 26. Distribution of the average diameter of embryonic roots in bread wheat (adjusted genotypic means) in the aeroponics experiment (estimated from all embryonic tip measurements during a 15 day-long period).

7.2.1.4 Seminal root angle

Figure 27. Distribution of the seminal root angle in bread wheat (adjusted genotypic means). Left panel: computed as the difference in direction of of the left- and right-most embryonic roots in the pouch experiment (3-day old plants). Right panel: computed as the angle between the first pair of seminal roots in aeroponics experiment measured manually from root scans between days 2 and 5. This second angle is logically narrower than the first. It is not confounded by the number of embryonic roots, but does not represent the angle of a second pair of seminal roots.

7.2.2 Lateral roots

7.2.2.1 Lateral root density

Figure 28. Distribution of the lateral root density in bread wheat (adjusted genotypic means) from the aeroponics experiment (estimated as the slope of a regression between the number of lateral root tips and the cumulated length of the branched zone of all embryonic roots over a 15 day-long period).

7.2.2.2 Duration of LRP development

Figure 29. Distribution of the duration of lateral root primordium development in bread wheat (adjusted genotypic means) from the aeroponics experiment (estimated over a 10 day-long period following the first LR emergence event).

7.2.2.3 Lateral root diameter

Figure 30. Distribution of the average diameter of lateral roots in bread wheat (adjusted genotypic means) in the aeroponics experiment (estimated from all LR tip measurements during a 15 day-long period).

7.2.3 Integrative variables

7.2.3.1 Convex hull area

Figure 31. Distribution of the convex hull area in bread wheat (adjusted genotypic means). Left panel: pouch experiment (3-day old plants). Right panel: rhizotube experiment (15 day-old plants).

7.2.3.2 Cumulated root length

Figure 32. Distribution of the cumulated root length in bread wheat (adjusted genotypic means). Left panel: cumulated length of embryonic roots in the pouch experiment (3-day old plants). Right panel: cumulated projected area of embryonic (sometimes with few nodals) and lateral roots from 15 day-old plants in the rhizotube experiment. Under a few assumptions, this projected area can be considered as a proxy for total root length.

7.2.3.3 Root system width

Figure 33. Distribution of the width of the root system in bread wheat (adjusted genotypic means), computed from the width of the bounding rectangle of the root system of 15-day old plants.

7.2.3.4 Root:shoot ratio

Figure 34. Distribution of the root-shoot ratio in bread wheat (adjusted genotypic means). Left panel: 15-day old plants in the rhizotube experiment. Right panel: 15-day old plants in the aeroponics experiment.

7.3 Genotypic means distributions from durum wheat platforms experiments

7.3.1 Embryonic roots (seminal and primary)

Figure 35. Distribution of the number of embryonic roots in durum wheat (adjusted genotypic means).

Figure 36. Distribution of embryonic root length in durum wheat (adjusted genotypic means). Left panel: average root length in the pouch experiment (3-days old seedlings). Right panel: elongation rate of the oldest embryonic root (primary) in the aeroponics experiment (estimated over a 15 day-long period).

Figure 37. Distribution of the length of the longest embryonic root (usually the oldest) in durum wheat (adjusted genotypic means). Left panel: rhizotube experiment (15-day old plants). Right panel: aeroponics experiment (15 day-old plants).

Figure 38. Distribution of the average diameter of embryonic roots in durum wheat (adjusted genotypic means) in the aeroponics experiment (estimated from all embryonic tip measurements during a 15 day-long period).

Figure 39. Distribution of the seminal root angle in durum wheat (adjusted genotypic means). Left panel: computed as the difference in direction of the left- and right-most embryonic roots in the pouch experiment (3-day old plants). Right panel: computed as the angle between the first pair of seminal roots in aeroponics experiment measured manually from root scans between days 2 and 5. This second angle is logically narrower than the first. It is not confounded by the number of embryonic roots, but does not represent the angle of a second pair of seminal roots.

7.3.2 Lateral roots

Figure 40. Distribution of the lateral root density in durum wheat (adjusted genotypic means) from the aeroponics experiment (estimated as the slope of a regression between the number of lateral root tips and the cumulated length of the branched zone of all embryonic roots over a 15 day-long period).

Figure 41. Distribution of the duration of lateral root primordium development in durum wheat (adjusted genotypic means) from the aeroponics experiment (estimated over a 10 day-long period following the first LR emergence event).

Figure 42. Distribution of the average diameter of lateral roots in durum wheat (adjusted genotypic means) in the aeroponics experiment (estimated from all LR tip measurements during a 15 day-long period).

7.3.3 Integrative variables

Figure 43. Distribution of the convex hull area in durum wheat (adjusted genotypic means). Left panel: pouch experiment (3-day old plants). Right panel: rhizotube experiment (15 day-old plants).

Figure 44. Distribution of the cumulated root length in durum wheat (adjusted genotypic means). Left panel: cumulated length of embryonic roots in the pouch experiment (3-day old plants). Right panel: cumulated projected area of embryonic (sometimes with few nodals) and lateral roots from 15 day-old plants in the rhizotube experiment. Under a few assumptions, this projected area can be considered as a proxy for total root length.

Figure 45. Distribution of the width of the root system in durum wheat (adjusted genotypic means), computed from the width of the bounding rectangle of the root system of 15-day old plants.

Figure 46. Distribution of the root:shoot ratio in durum wheat (adjusted genotypic means). Left panel: 15-day old plants in the rhizotube experiment. Right panel: 15-day old plants in the aeroponics experiment.